

THE ANALYSIS OF MODERN PROBLEMS OF ENSURING THE PROTECTION OF PUBLIC ORDER DURING MASS EVENTS

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Annotation. The article analyzes the theoretical foundations and the current state of ensuring public order and security during mass events.

Key words: mass event, public order, public security, social and political mass events, international mass events, territorial and local mass events.

Аннотация. В статье проанализированы теоретические основы и нынешнее состояние обеспечения общественного порядка и безопасности при проведении массовых мероприятий.

Опорные понятия: массовое мероприятие, общественный порядок, общественная безопасность, общественно-политические массовые мероприятия, международные массовые мероприятия, территориальные и местные массовые мероприятия.

Currently, in accordance with the current legal acts, the concept of "public event" is defined in the Republic of Uzbekistan as follows: "entertainment, theater, concert, sports, advertising programs and other entertainment programs, as well as national, religious, professional holidays with the participation of at least 250 people, as well as the Assembly of individuals in open and closed buildings, premises, buildings and other places is recognized as a public event."

It should be noted that unauthorized mass events are illegal and measures, and as a result of the measures taken by the competent authorities (internal affairs bodies) are subject to termination. Authorized mass events are carried out by security and public order forces in three stages: preparation, conduct and final stage.

If we take into account that currently in Tashkent every day held about a hundred weddings and other ceremonies involving 500 or more citizens, it must be recognized that measures to ensure fire safety, road safety, public order and security are not fully implemented in the conduct of these activities.

Thus, none of these events does not meet the requirements of the legislation governing the holding of mass events.

Article 33 of the Constitution clearly stipulates that mass events must be held only on legal grounds. Citizens have the right to manifest their public activity in the form of meetings, assemblies and demonstrations in accordance

with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The authorities have the right to suspend or prohibit such measures only in terms of security.¹

There are two interpretations of public order in existing sources of literature on state and law: broad and narrow.

In a narrow sense, social order is a complex, multifaceted social phenomenon. The system resulting from the application of administrative law, criminal law and social law between public order bodies and the public is a system of social relations. Such acts carried out at mass events, such as the prosecution of citizens and other similar acts that violate public order and the safety of citizens, are considered to be petty hooliganism, if such actions by their nature do not require criminal punishment for their Commission.

Therefore, modern legislation and practice are faced with a new approach to the disclosure of the essence of public order and the development of key national measures to protect it.

E.F. Kolontaevsky believes that public order is a system of social relations that creates conditions for the activities of enterprises, institutions and public organizations and ensures public safety².

The main features of ensuring public order and security during mass actions are:

- first of all, the involvement of the public as a participant (spectator);
- organization of mass movements with predetermined goals and implemented on the initiative of certain entities;
- holding in public places.

According to the Russian scientist D. A. Korotchenkov, it is also extremely important that public order and security of mass events are legal or illegal³.

It is advisable to divide organized mass actions into legal and illegal, depending on its nature. At the same time, in our opinion, illegal mass events can also be divided into two types:

1) illegal mass events that do not cause serious damage to public order and public safety include "illegal meetings, rallies, street protests and demonstrations that do not disrupt the work of transport, communication organizations based on violence»;

2) mass organized actions (riots) that seriously threaten public safety and public order.

¹ Constitution of The Republic of Uzbekistan. – T: Uzbekistan, 2018. – 76 p.

² Kolontaevsky F. B. Organization and improvement of activity of public security police. Textbook – M. Academy of the Russian Interior Ministry. – 1995. – 245p.

³ Korotchenkov D. A. Problems of legal regulation of the organization and holding of public events. – Law and law – 2006 – № 7.

The purpose of such division of illegal mass actions is identification of legal norms of use of special means by subjects providing a public order and safety (law-enforcement bodies, etc.)⁴.

Public order is primarily based on the law and other social norms, which are designed to ensure public order and public safety of citizens, the normal functioning of state institutions and public institutions, the protection of the constitutional right of citizens, respect for human dignity and social morality, as well as developing as a system of voluntary social relations. In General, the concept of "personal security of citizens" can be described as the protection of every citizen from unlawful attacks on his life, health, rights and freedoms, dignity, personality and inviolability of residence.

The above is evident in the fact that they are closely linked to individual security, public security and measures taken to ensure the safety of citizens. Such a relationship not only means that the security of every human being depends on the security of society, but that public security also means saving many lives at the same time in a country or city, in a locality and in a certain area.

According to S. T. Akhmedova, the protection of public order includes ensuring the safety of citizens. The main direction of the internal Affairs bodies in carrying out these activities is the maintenance of public order, and ensuring public order in itself ensures the safety of citizens⁵.

The threat to public safety can arise in case of violation of the rules of operation of means of rail, river, road transport, non-compliance with traffic rules, violation of safety rules during the construction process, road construction and other works, the operation of flammable objects and devices when handling firearms, ammunition, explosive materials, highly toxic substances, radioactive isotopes and other dangerous objects and things.

Violation of the above-mentioned norms for society in accordance with the criminal law is considered a criminal offence against public security. At the same time, such offences also violate the private security of citizens. Public order is an integral part of public administration. Therefore, it is very important that it be considered in various aspects, including in terms of the description of the object and its impact.

⁴ Korotchenkov D. A. Problems of legal regulation of the organization and holding of public events. – Law and law – 2006 – № 7.

⁵ Akhmedova S. Association of lawyers and Association of advocates of the Republic of Tajikistan. ITCM, T – 2001. - 14 pages.

In the process of protection of public order influence on human behavior is using a variety of administrative or organizational forms and methods. Administrative and legal forms of influence on the behavior of people are carried out by authorized persons and through the adoption of regulations by officials. Public order and personal danger to citizens arise from violations of the established procedure for holding mass events, not preparing a place for them and timely response to the actions of large groups of people.

The implementation of public security measures is a guarantee of normal and other offences committed by the public and the competent authorities and organizations in order to ensure that people are held accountable, in the workplace and in the satisfaction of their material and spiritual needs, civil rights and freedoms, as well as in the exercise of the rights and freedoms of citizens aimed at preventing the consequences of damage, natural disasters and other measures.

According to scientists who have conducted research in this area, a complex, complex feature of public order and security implies the need to create a variety of tools and methods for their protection. Based on the features of measures to regulate public relations in the areas studied, the following types of public order and public security are distinguished: administrative-legal, operational-legal, criminal-legal, civil-legal⁶.

According to this classification, the basic legal rules governing the protection of public order can be divided into two groups:

- 1) legal norms regulating the behavior of citizens in the field of public order protection and establishing responsibility for their violation;
- 2) rules that define the forms, objectives, powers, functions and responsibilities of public authorities and their officials in the sphere of protection of public order.

Social goals and content of normative documents in the classification of their legal impact on public order are primarily reflected in the description of the normative model of behavior, which largely corresponds to the needs of society. By strengthening the rules of conduct, the rules of law are binding on them and define the rights and duties of citizens in society. The morality of citizens in the sphere of public order is based on the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which strengthens the rights and freedoms of man and citizen.

As President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev stressed: "the Principle of the rule of law enshrined in the Constitution is an important

⁶ Rossinsky B. V., Starilov Yu. N. Administrative law. – M. – Norm, 2010 – P. 98.

guarantee of the protection of human rights and freedoms in our society and the effective implementation of all reforms."⁷

Legislative documents relating to public order establish responsibility for their non-compliance and a ban on certain actions. In particular, article 15 of the administrative liability Code establishes administrative liability for offences that violate public order. Based on the analysis of the above-mentioned problems, we believe that it is now necessary to adopt the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the procedure for holding mass events" and to amend a number of laws regulating the provision of public security during mass events.

⁷ The report of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyev the solemn meeting devoted to the 24th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

